

Formation of A Strategic Management Model for Enterprises on The Basis of a Fractal Approach

Svetlana DROBYAZKO

Doctor of Economics, Professor, President of the European Academy of Sciences, London, United Kingdom
svetlana.drobyazko@yahoo.com

Yuliia MELNIKOVA

Senior Lecturer, Dnipro University of Technology, Ukraine
melnikova_yuliia@ua.fm

Abstract

Based on fractal theory and the provisions on fractal structuring concerning socio-economic systems, the essence of the restaurant business has been defined as a complex, unstable, self-similar, fractal production and service system that seeks for self-development; a conceptual model of the system of the restaurant industry functional fractal determinants (range, technology, management, marketing, development dynamics and hierarchy) and a fractal model of the restaurant industry by organizational approach have been developed (person, position, unit, enterprise, merger of enterprises (network, cluster) restaurant services market). On the basis of the basic evolutionary principles system (necessity, sufficiency, controllability, self-organization, variability, structural-functional systematic, unity and infinity), a hierarchy of enterprises fractal determinants in the restaurant industry was formed.

Keywords: Fractal Theory, Strategic Management, Hierarchy, Determinants, Development.

Introduction

Fractal as an independent structural unit of the enterprise in the process of functioning set and formulate their tasks. Fractals can change, reappear and disintegrate. The peculiarity of fractals is their self-organization, which results in clusters occurrence. The clustering condition is the absence of external pressure and the formation of a common goal for the cluster as a higher-level organization system. Fractals also have centralized functions that are related to the special data that cannot be stored permanently in subfractals. An important point in demonstrating the feature of fractal self-organization is that good ideas come true no matter where they came from. Therefore, one of the most important requirements for an official, unit or enterprise within a merger, as a "fractal factory", is their ability to entrepreneurial thinking and activity.

Fractal does not always remain in the superfractal system, it can also become completely independent. Thus, the closely related companies occurs.

Literature Survey

Modern scientists distinguish separate rigid self-similarity regarding invariance of large-scale transformations and non-rigid (covariant) (Aguinis, H., Edwards, J. R., & Bradley, K. J. (2017)). That is, we are talking about linear and nonlinear fractals. The first is characterized by absolutely accurate adherence to the principle of self-similarity. In nonlinear fractals, the affine principle is maintained with less intensity.

Analysis of the literature allows us to formulate the major feature of fractals - self-similarity, which can be traced at any level of the functional hierarchy (Arsenyev, Y., et al. (2019); Drobyazko, S., et al. (2020)): striving for optimal organization of functional relationships; setting boundaries; formation of central structures; maintaining the fractal structures integrity; ensuring a certain defined development time (cycle); formation of periphery and formation of attractive goals.

The study of socio-economic processes should be based not on the geometric concept of self-similarity (fractality), but on its structural and essential content, that is, rather, on the fractality principle (Hitt, M., & Duane Ireland, R. (2017)). In this case, fractality can be viewed from two interrelated positions: the fractality of the systems (their

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structures, elements) involved in the process, and the fractality of the processes that determine the level of enterprise development.

Identifying self-similar structures gives new opportunities to manage the ability of choosing priorities based on the concordance of internal and external resources with the influence of environmental factors, of the external environment, which determines the scientific task of finding effective mechanisms for strategic management of the development processes and self-development of restaurants (Meyer, G. D., Neck, H. M., & Meeks, M. D. (2017)).

An important feature of fractals is their small dimension, the value of which for economic units is determined the following ways (Durmanov, A., et al. (2019)): the area of dimensional resources; functional and structural features of production and service; the goals and tasks of the enterprise, as well as its history.

At different hierarchical levels (region, enterprise, part of enterprise) it is possible to identify self-similar dimensional socio-economic structures and self-constructing ones, which have similar trajectories and elements of development (production, service, sales, cash flows, social, cultural, etc.) (Trigeorgis, L., & Reuer, J. J. (2017)).

Methods

The following set of general scientific and special research methods is used in the work: logical analysis - when constructing the logic and structure of work; systematization and comparison - to clarify and order the conceptual apparatus for strategic management of restaurant business; methods of data grouping and generalization - in the calculation of strategic development indicators by the group of selected enterprises for the restaurant industry; systematic and process approach - to substantiate methodological support for assessing the level of strategic management effectiveness of enterprises and its components.

Results

Based on the taxonomy method, it becomes possible to construct a generalized assessment of a complex entity, such as restaurant business or process, such as strategic management.

Relevant indicators are selected for assessment and further usage in the process of strategic management of the restaurant business according to the proposed fractal structure (Table 1).

Table 1: Fractal structure of the indicators system for assessment of strategic management effectiveness (author's development)

Fractal level	Fractal determinants of the enterprise	Strategic task	Indicators
Higher potential	Competitiveness	Ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise and the effectiveness of strategic management	Effectiveness of the strategic management
Hierarchy	Hierarchy	Obtaining and consolidation of the enterprise in a certain hierarchical place in the industry and inter-branch space (type, network, format, cluster)	Profitability
Evolution	Dynamics of development	Providing the necessary dynamics of the enterprise	Rate of the turnover change
System composition	Marketing	Ensuring maximum compliance between supply and demand	Turnover Turnover in place
Information (energy information)	Management	Ensure maximum compliance between the subject and the object of management	Labor productivity Completeness of strategic management functions implementation

Energy	Technology	Optimization of service technologies and production of goods, as well as effective functioning of providing structures	Quality of service Production quality
Elements	Assortment	Optimization of the assortment, improving the quality of restaurant products	Menu compliance with customer expectations Quality of restaurant products

Assessment of the strategic management effectiveness, which is carried out using taxonomic analysis by defined indicators, makes it possible to rank enterprises.

The fractal approach allows to distinguish the rates at six fractal levels and to gain a fractal profile of the strategic management effectiveness in the field of restaurant business.

An important step in the strategic management process is to determine further directions of the enterprise's development. In order to achieve this goal, the environment changes are forecasted in an optimistic, realistic and pessimistic scenario. Based on the evaluation of the strategic management effectiveness and the determination of the enterprise's rank, it becomes possible to determine the optimal boundaries of the forecasted goals.

The major indicators in solving this problem are the indicators of the strategic management of the in the group within the companies under study, the outsider, as well as the enterprise that is the object of research. Goals due to the realistic prediction may lie between the levels of the research entity and the enterprise-leader. According to optimistic forecasts, fractal effectiveness indicators will exceed the level of the leader. According to the pessimistic forecast fractal effectiveness indicators will be lower than those achieved by the enterprise - the object of study (Table 2).

Table 2: Opportunities of fractal levels strategic development in the field of restaurant business according to different forecasts (author's development)

Forecast	Fractal levels of the enterprises in the field of restaurant business					
	1 Assortment	2 Technology	3 Management	4 Marketing	5 Development dynamics	6 Hierarchy
Optimistic	Exceeding the leader level by a certain group of enterprises or reaching the level of a leader by a certain group of enterprises					
Realistic	Reaching the leader level for a specific group of enterprises or maintaining the existing level of a company in a specific group					
Pessimistic	Maintaining an existing enterprise level by a specified group or reducing an existing enterprise level by a specified group					

However, this applies to indicators whose values are largely depend on consumer preferences. No one will reduce the quality of products, services and strategic management by the law of self-preservation. Strategic enterprise management includes the process of forming aim system. Achieving (maintaining) a certain level of competitiveness is a higher level aim.

Analysis of research regarding goal setting and strategic planning shows the diversity of approaches and classification systems of goals. In our opinion, the goals of the second hierarchical level should be grouped in three directions: improvement of structure and quality of goods, improvement of market relations, as well as optimization of internal resources.

For each direction, the goal is specified by the certain parameters - the nature and pace of change in the quality or amount of the object. Thus, for restaurant products, the technical and economic characteristics of quality are determined, as well as the period of its achievement. Target consumers, volume and specific weight are important for the market.

The second level goals are specified in the third level of the "goal tree". Thus, the direction of improving the "status" of a product is specified by improving product's quality in accordance with the changed norms and

determining an adequate price. The direction of work concerning the market is specified by the work on market research and measures of influence on the market (advertising).

With regard to internal resources, it is advisable to clarify the obtaining methods of all types of resources (raw materials, equipment, information, finance, personnel, organizational and management resources, etc.), as well as establish their interaction within technological processes, and organize a strategic management system.

Personnel should be distinguished as a separate third-level aim due to its special nature. The created hierarchy of goals regarding the restaurant business becomes an important condition for choosing an effective algorithm of actions. The interaction of these elements is basic for a system (person, unit or enterprise) to achieve a high level of competitiveness.

Discussion

Taking into account the multidimensionality of the enterprises activity, as well as the fulfillment of special basic and additional functions, a conceptual model of the system of functional fractal determinants in the restaurant industry has been developed. Its essence lies in the hierarchical organization of fractal determinants (assortment, technology, management, marketing, dynamics of development, hierarchy), united on the basis of evolutionary principles, and a fractal model of the restaurant business by organizational approach (person, position, unit, enterprise, organization) merger of enterprises (network, cluster), restaurant services market).

Based on the strategic management analysis, it is proposed to define it as an activity that aims to create competitive advantages, achieve sustainability and flexibility of the enterprise in the long run due to human potential with the predominance of proactive management style, development and implementation of effective strategies that provide not only necessary reaction, but also capable of influencing the environment, based on the vision of the enterprise future image and due to the high dynamic organizational capabilities of fractal determinants to self-development. Taking into account the structure of the strategies as well as the main content and types of strategic activities, a list of strategic functions to be implemented by the restaurants is proposed.

Conclusion

Using fractal theory, the decomposition of the restaurant management system into main components was performed, which made it possible to form a system of qualitative (quality of restaurant products, concordance between menus and consumer expectations, quality of goods and service) and quantitative (completeness of strategic management functions, productivity, turnover, turnover per 1 seat, rate of change in turnover, profitability) strategic management performance evaluation indicators.

Taking into account, the high degree of uncertainty and variability of the environment, it is recommended to formulate an impact forecast of business environment factors using an optimistic, realistic and pessimistic scenario. In order to respond adequately to the environmental impact, for each variant of the forecasted scenario, expedient strategic development boundaries were outlined, which focus on the enterprise's own achievements and the achievements of the leader of the respective restaurant enterprise group.

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